

Model-Based Security Analysis of Interconnected Subsystems: A Methodology for Security Compatibility Evaluation

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Abstract—Integrating subsystems developed by different manufacturers is a challenging task. Nevertheless, in fields like Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), it is imperative for vehicles and infrastructure to constantly communicate. The proposed method models elements from a Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) of each subsystem using SysML. Then it applies compatibility conditions to the exported model to generate an output compatibility statement. This statement indicates whether the subsystems are compatible from a security perspective or not. The method enables subsystems to assess their potential for secure integration allowing for independent development by manufacturers. We implement the method and evaluate it on an industrial use case to showcase the method’s ability to determine the security compatibility of two subsystems.

Index Terms—Automotive Security, Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment, TARA, MBSE, Autonomous Vehicles, Smart Infrastructure, Compositionality, ITS

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern vehicles increasingly rely on external information to provide novel and useful functionality. This information can support general awareness of the environment for the driver, provide useful information while navigating, and even support autonomous driving decisions directly made by the vehicle. Systems which support a vehicle with external information are called Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), which typically communicate with a vehicle via different communication channels. ITS allow for coordination between different vehicles, provide infrastructure support, or backend data, and allow for more efficient traffic management and increased road safety.

When ITS information is used for autonomous driving decisions, the correctness of this data becomes crucial to the road users safety. Furthermore, attackers can use ITS to harm users of cars by attacking an infrastructure system instead of directly attacking the vehicle, which in turn provides manipulated information to the vehicle. Hence, the security of a vehicle

now depends on the security of external systems. Typically, the infrastructure system and the vehicle are provided by different organizations, which may not know about each other during development of the respective systems. Therefore, analyzing the security of the overall system consisting of a vehicle and an infrastructure becomes a huge challenge.

In this paper, we provide a method that allows the compositional analysis of the security of a system, whose security depends on external, unknown systems. This analysis is based on explicit assumptions about how well the external system protects information the analyzed system depends on. Using our method, through evaluating our developed compatibility conditions, it can be assessed if an external system satisfies the assumptions made by the first system about it. This assessment can be done during the integration of the systems, or even during runtime of the systems in the field. The information required to be exchanged to evaluate these conditions is limited, so that the intellectual property of a system which has to be released is kept to a minimum. Based on the result of the compatibility conditions, a decision can be made, if and how the systems can cooperate.

In this paper, we build upon the conceptual C-TAR method proposed by Abdelsalam et al. [1], which determines the security compatibility of two subsystems which form an overall system. The first contribution of this paper is developing a custom SysML [2] profile for modeling method specific elements in addition to threat and risk analysis (TARA) elements. Secondly, our method generates essential-information files that provides manufacturers the ability to keep information exchange to a minimum to check the compatibility between their subsystems.

Thirdly, we introduce the concept of common information list (CIL) to help identify and match assets between the different subsystems. Finally, we evaluate our method by

applying it to an industrial use case. We show that modeling a TARA for a system with our method is relatively straight forward, if the user is familiar with industrial standard TARAs.

In our proposed method, using the SysML model of a TARA, information is extracted to be used for a compatibility judgement. We apply three compatibility conditions based on this information which have to be satisfied in order to ensure that two subsystems can securely cooperate. Further, we show that our method is able to provide information about whether two subsystems are compatible with respect to security, and, if not, what the reason for incompatibility is.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II discusses related work in the literature and Section III provides some background information needed for the context of this paper. In Section IV, we describe the method and in Section V we discuss the method application on an industrial use case in addition to evaluating the method. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section VI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses some of the related work. In the work presented of [3] and [4], they use SysML modeling in the security domain. In [3], they propose the SysML-Sec method which focuses on facilitating the collaboration between security experts and system designers. While in [4] they propose SecML which aims to provide a structured approach of modeling security requirements, threats, vulnerabilities, and defenses in a systematic manner.

The work of [5] introduces the IoTsecM approach which allows the representation of security requirements in UML and SysML. IoTsecM aims to model security requirements in IoT systems to guide developers during the design of IoT systems. While in [6], they proposed a meta-model that captures assets, estimates the impact of damage scenarios, identifies threats and assesses their feasibility.

According to [6], most of the steps in the automotive development process are already model-based. Therefore, using a model-based risk assessment is highly beneficial to support the identification of assets, vulnerabilities, threats and countermeasures. The work we present in this paper relies on SysML modeling to enable the user to model elements such as assets, threats and security properties. We use SysML to make uniform the varying input of different manufacturers to our method.

In this survey [7], the authors provide a comprehensive security analysis for vehicular networks while this survey [8] provides a review of the solutions for the security of V2X communications. This survey [9] analyzes threats and some security solutions for V2X. Further, this survey [10] discusses TARA methods in the automotive field and in this survey [11], the authors discuss security issues that hinder Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and existing security solutions in the literature.

Reference [12] states that ISO-21434 [13] provides a standard for automotive security, but it does not provide automated

methods in terms of saving more effort and time in creating secure system architectures. Therefore, they propose a concept to automate the TARA method creating secure system-of-systems (SoS) architectures that conforms with ISO-21434. Furthermore, in the work of [14] and [15], they propose approaches for automating threat modeling and risk assessment to help identify risks, assets, threats and related countermeasures.

The surveys discuss different aspects of automotive security, such as TARA methods and security countermeasures, but they do not discuss a TARA method of heterogeneous interdependent subsystems. Also, the discussed methods in the previous paragraph perform risk analysis individually for each system which results in identifying threats specific to each system. While in our work, we focus on threats that are interdependent between subsystems.

The work of [16] investigates the interdependencies between the cyber and the physical components of such systems. They propose a risk assessment method that finds dependencies between the assets that might be exploited by attackers. While they determine the risk that is due to the dependencies of cyber and physical components, in our work, we evaluate systems that have interdependent attack paths through applying a set of compatibility conditions to their elements.

Organizations and manufacturers need to protect their intellectual property as well as reduce complexity of the development process, therefore full information sharing is neither desirable nor possible. The work proposed in [17] proposes an interface between organizations to share required information and allows them to perform risk assessment in a collaborative way. In comparison to our work, we present a method to determine the compatibility of two subsystems at either design time or runtime.

In the works of [18] and [19], the authors present the concept of Digital Dependability Identity (DDI) that is used to assure the dependability of cyber physical systems in design time and runtime. They define a DDI as an analyzable and potentially executable model of information about the dependability of a component or system that contains unique information to describe the dependability of a system.

They aim to use DDIs to express heterogenous dependability information across different manufacturers with a focus on the dependability property of safety. While in our work, the aim is to express security information such as assets and security properties between manufacturers to help them evaluate their systems' compatibility.

III. TARA IN THE AUTOMOTIVE CONTEXT

This section provides an overview of TARA according to ISO/SAE 21434 [13]. The aim of a TARA is to identify the threats a system is exposed to and the risks associated to these threats. The TARA output helps in making decisions to deal with the identified risks.

The first step in a TARA is defining the system and describing its interfaces and functions, then, assets are identified. An asset is anything worth protecting in the system such as the CAN bus in a car. Each asset is assigned at least one security

property which has to be protected. Confidentiality, integrity, and availability of an asset are typical security properties. A threat is defined as the non-fulfillment of a security property of an asset. For example, if the integrity of communication via the CAN bus is identified as the security property to be protected, the manipulation of the communication is the threat.

A damage scenario is provided for each threat describing the consequences of realising that threat. Each damage scenario has an impact rating which quantifies the consequences of a damage scenario. For the aforementioned threat of manipulation of CAN bus communication, a damage scenario can be an unintended breaking of the vehicle, which can lead to the impact of loss of life.

In order to estimate the probability of a threat, the standard provides a rating of the required effort by an attacker in order to realise the threat, the Attack Feasibility Rating (AFR). The first step to provide the AFR for a threat is to identify the attack paths an attacker could use to realise a threat. An attack path is a sequence of actions an attacker performs leading to the realization of the threat. Each attack path identified is rated with an AFR. Using the rating of an attack path and the impact of a threat determine the risk of a threat.

The standard offers several methods to determine the AFR but our focus here is on the attack potential method. The attack potential method requires to rate each attack path with five attributes: the time an attacker requires to perform the actions of the attack path, the amount of expertise required by the attacker, the level of knowledge needed about the product, the window of opportunity required to perform the attack (access), and finally the type of equipment the attacker needs. Each rated category of an attack path is translated into an attack potential value as shown in table I. Finally, the AFR together with the impact of a threat can then be translated into a qualitative risk value.

Elapsed time		Specialist expertise		Knowledge of the item or component		Window of opportunity		Equipment	
Enumerate	Value	Enumerate	Value	Enumerate	Value	Enumerate	Value	Enumerate	Value
≤1 day	0	Layman	0	Public	0	Unlimited	0	Standard	0
≤1 week	1	Proficient	3	Restricted	3	Easy	1	Specialized	4
≤1 month	4	Expert	6	Confidential	7	Moderate	4	Bespoke	7
≤6 months	17	Multiple experts	8	Strictly confidential	11	Difficult/none	10	Multiple bespoke	9
>6 months	19								

TABLE I
ISO 21434 ATTRIBUTE RATINGS TABLE [13]

In this paper, we build upon the previous work of Abdelsalam et al. [1]. In their work, they present a method called C-TAR on a conceptual level which evaluates the security compatibility of two subsystems. In the following paragraphs, we elaborate on some of their notions that we build upon in this paper.

Firstly, they present the notion of dependent asset (d-asset). According to them, a d-asset is used in a TARA of a system to reflect the dependency of this system's TARA to an external system's TARA. This occurs when the system under evaluation has a critical connection to the external system and the knowledge of the system under evaluation is not enough

to rate all relevant attack paths. Also, the d-asset is given a security property and a rating. The attack path which contains the d-asset is referred to as a dependent attack path.

To illustrate the concept of a d-asset, Fig.1 shows an example of how a d-asset in one TARA acts as a placeholder for the missing information of another TARA. In this example the vehicle's TARA has the threat *manipulate vehicle behavior*. This threat could be realised through several actions in an attack path of the vehicle's TARA. One of the actions in this attack path is to steal the security certificate from the infrastructure. Since the infrastructure is not part of the vehicle, there is a dependency between the infrastructure and the vehicle. Information about the infrastructure is necessary to complete the vehicle's TARA, yet with information being limited to the vehicle, the effort required to steal the certificate from the infrastructure is unknown.

Fig. 1. D-asset Illustrative Example

Using the concept of d-asset, the dependency between the vehicle and the infrastructure can be represented since it allows the vehicle's TARA to quantify the effort needed to steal the certificate, representing a requirement for secure connection to an external system. The vehicle's TARA does not have the necessary information to rate the action "Steal Certificate" so it uses a d-asset as a placeholder in the attack path. This d-asset corresponds to all attack paths that realise the threat "Extract Wi-Fi Certificate" from the infrastructure TARA as shown in Fig.1. Giving a rating for the d-asset in the vehicle's TARA allows for comparing this rating to the rating of the corresponding attack paths in the infrastructure TARA acting as a requirement from the vehicle to the infrastructure.

Secondly, they develop a set of compatibility conditions to evaluate the compatibility of two subsystems. According to them, two subsystems A and B are compatible, if for every attack path that contains a d-asset in the TARA of subsystem A the following conditions are satisfied:

- **Assets Condition:** There exists an asset $Asset_B$ in the TARA of subsystem B where $d-asset_A = asset_B$, and
- **Security Property Condition:** There exists a security property $property_B$ for $asset_B$ in the TARA of B where $property_A = property_B$, and
- **Rating Condition:** For every attack path for $asset_B$, $property_B$ and with rating (r_1B, \dots, r_nB) it holds that $r_{iA} \leq r_{iB}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, and

Fig. 2. Overview of C-TAR [1] and Our Method

- Vice versa with A and B exchanged in the conditions above.

If all three conditions are satisfied, then the two subsystems under evaluation are compatible, i.e. they form an overall secure system. The first condition checks if a d-asset of one subsystem is considered as an asset in the other subsystem. The second condition checks if the matched assets from the first condition have the security properties of the matched d-asset or not. While the third condition, checks if the rating of the d-asset is less than or equal that of all attack paths associated with the asset in the other subsystem. The rating consists of five attributes, referred to previously in section III, which are time, expertise, knowledge, access and equipment.

Essentially, the compatibility conditions state that for two subsystems under evaluation, any attack involving the d-asset requires that all attack paths for the threat in system B are at least as hard as assumed in System's A d-asset rating. Therefore, the provided result of applying the compatibility conditions is correct under the condition that all attack paths associated with a d-asset attack path are at least as hard or harder. Therefore, using the compatibility conditions, C-TAR identifies the attack path with least resistance, providing an evaluation of two subsystems security compatibility. Therefore, in the context of this paper, the compatibility conditions are well suited for our use case.

Lastly, they develop the concept of a compatibility statement which is the output of C-TAR, such statement contains the verdict about the compatibility of the two subsystems under evaluation.

Fig.2 shows a summary of the work of Abdelsalam et al. [1], marked in blue, and our work in this paper, marked in orange. Their work could be summarized into four main steps: using an ISO 21434 compliant TARA, identifying the required elements to extract from a TARA, determining the compatibility conditions, and defining the structure of the compatibility statement.

Looking at their work, we identified four gaps that we aim to address in this paper. First, their work did not specify how to input the TARAs into the method. Second, they did not specify how to extract the required information from the TARA to

apply the compatibility conditions. Third, they did not have an implementation to generate a compatibility statement. Fourth, they applied their method on a theoretical example with no evaluation.

We expand upon their work and fill the gaps of their method. First, we modeled the input TARAs to have a uniform input to the method. Second, we developed an automated script to extract the TARA information for further processing. Third, we developed an implementation to generate the compatibility statement. Fourth, we test our method on an industrial use case and evaluate it.

IV. METHOD DESCRIPTION

In this section, we describe our proposed approach and discuss the main improvements made over the work of Abdelsalam et al [1]. An overview of the method is shown in Fig.2. The method comprises of three phases, each of which is discussed in detail in the following sections. The first phase of the method is TARA modeling. In this phase, the user utilizes our SysML profile to model the TARA of the subsystem. Following that is the processing phase which processes the exported model of the modeling phase to extract the information required to apply the compatibility conditions. In the final phase of the method, the method checks the compatibility conditions to generate the output compatibility statement.

A. First Phase - TARA Modeling

In the first phase of the method, the user models the TARA of each subsystem using our developed SysML profile. The primary objective of modeling the TARA is to generate a uniform input format, to use in the subsequent phases of the method. TARAs tend to have inherent differences in form, structure and convention across different manufacturers. These variations make it challenging to conduct a meaningful comparison between TARAs across different manufacturers. Additionally, no TARA modeling tools or languages support the concept of d-assets, which is central to our approach. Therefore, we develop our own SysML profile suitable for our method.

We provide a SysML [2] profile, which defines a language extension of SysML for modeling TARA elements needed by our method such as d-assets. For the development of the metamodel of our extension, we started by specifying requirements for our design decisions, followed by conceptual modeling and then SysML profile design.

1) *Requirement and Design Decisions*: The development of the modeling profile necessitates clear requirements. The requirements for our profile are summarized as follows.

a) *Requirement 1: TARA-Methods based on the ISO/SAE 21434*: The created modeling profile shall facilitate the modeling of the ISO/SAE 21434 [13] TARA elements.

b) *Requirement 2: Standard Systems Modeling Language*: To ensure seamless communication between stakeholders, we chose SysML as the modeling language for its versatility and widespread acceptance.

Fig. 3. Conceptual Overview of The Metamodel

c) *Requirement 3: Modeling Tool:* The profile must be compatible with a professional tool that supports SysML therefore, we selected Cameo Systems Modeler [20] as the modeling tool.

d) *Requirement 4: Ease of Use of the Tool:* The relationships between the elements defined by ISO/SAE 21434 [13] must be accurately represented ensuring a coherent and integrated model that reflects the intricacies of cybersecurity risk management.

e) *Requirement 5: Customizability:* The profile must be able to incorporate specific elements needed in our approach such as d-assets.

2) *Conceptual Overview of the Metamodel:* The second step in our development process involves creating a conceptual overview of the metamodel. This overview provides domain-specific information about the elements necessary for performing the C-TAR method and the relationships between these elements. Fig.3 presents the conceptual overview of the metamodel, which is divided into two main parts: system architecture and C-TAR analysis.

This illustration enables us to describe the relationships between the system architecture and the security analysis. The term "item" refers to all components of the system architecture. The "items" can be enumerated in an item list and provided by the system architect to the security engineer for performing a security analysis.

Items deemed critical for protection are categorized as assets. These elements can be associated with security properties such as confidentiality, integrity, or availability. The violation of a security property of an asset results in a threat. Realizing such a threat necessitates the enactment of an attack path. Attack paths are given a rating, which evaluates the feasibility of the attack path in terms of time, expertise, knowledge, access, and equipment needed by the attacker. Attack paths consists of actions and d-asset is considered an action.

After elaborating on the requirements and our design decisions in addition to giving an overview of our conceptual metamodel, the following section will explain the design of the SysML profile.

3) *SysML Profile Design:* We created individual stereotypes to model the TARA elements. Stereotypes in SysML allow us to extend the standard SysML language with domain-specific terms that are not covered by the standard SysML elements [21]. Additionally, they enable us to customize the modeling language to our engineering needs. We also utilize the generalization relationship in SysML to represent relationships between different elements in a model and to inherit the default properties of a block for our domain-specific elements, each defined with specific properties according to ISO/SAE 21434 [13]. Below, we explain the created elements and their attributes. Fig.4 shows the complete SysML profile used to model the different TARA elements.

a) *Assets:* Using a stereotype, we model the TARA element "asset" accompanied with four key attributes: The description, a string to provide details about the asset; the component, linking elements of the logical architecture considered as assets; property, where each asset is associated with one or more security property, utilizing an enumeration element of SysML; and the common information list (CIL).

We introduce to our method the concept of CIL which is derived from the stereotype "Common Information Object". We introduce the CIL concept to allow mapping of assets to d-assets and vice versa across the different subsystems. Since subsystems are developed by different manufacturers, there is no common convention for assets and d-assets. Therefore, we introduce the CIL to serve as common ground to match the different assets and d-assets between the different systems according to a defined protocol.

This list is created based on the protocol two systems use to communicate. Since systems' communication is defined through an interface, this serves as the basis for defining the CIL. Therefore, the CIL is a list of assets derived from the common protocol used by the two subsystems being evaluated. Using the CIL, the method determines the matching assets or d-assets between both subsystems.

b) *Attack Paths:* We model attack paths by first selecting an attack modeling technique. According to [22], techniques are categorized into use case methods, temporal methods, and graph-based methods. We chose Attack Trees, a graph-based method, for our SysML profile. An attack path is defined as a sequence of actions an attacker performs to realize a threat. In our profile, designing an attack tree uses four elements: threat, actions, "AND" and "OR" logical relations. Action refers to steps an attacker need to take to realize a threat while "AND" and "OR" blocks are used to connect two or more actions.

We model an attack path using attack tree stereotype while enabling the user to construct the attack tree of the attack path. Fig.5 shows an example of an attack path in the profile. The figure shows the threat "Manipulate Vehicle Behavior" and the actions that constitute the attack tree of such threat. The attack path has two attributes, the "attack feasibility rating" and "threat". How to calculate the attack path rating from ratings of actions (and d-assets in our case) is beyond the scope of this work. The interested reader is referred to Mauw et al. [23] which provides useful insights on attack trees and

Fig. 4. SysML Profile

calculating attack paths ratings.

We defined attack feasibility rating as a stereotype. Each rating has the five attributes of time, expertise, knowledge, access, and equipment, each of them utilized an enumeration element of SysML.

c) *D-assets*: A d-asset is modeled using a stereotype and its associated attributes are rating, CIL and security property. It is modeled as an action in an attack path.

According to Abdelsalam et al. [1], a d-asset is used to reflect the dependency of a system's TARA to another external system's TARA. Given a vehicle system under evaluation, this system may have an attack path which has a dependency to an infrastructure system. The knowledge of the vehicle system is not enough to rate all of its attack paths. In order to rate a vehicle's attack path, knowledge about each action in this attack path is needed. If the knowledge about an action is missing and is connected to the infrastructure system, a d-asset is used to represent such an action. Therefore, the d-asset would be used to represent the action in the vehicle's attack path which is dependent on the infrastructure system.

In an example of a vehicle that is connected to an infrastructure system. The vehicle's TARA has the threat *manipulate vehicle behavior*. This threat could be realised through several actions in an attack path of the vehicle's TARA, Fig.5. One of the actions in this attack path is to steal the infrastructure security certificate. Since the security certificate belongs to the infrastructure, there is a dependency between the infrastructure and the vehicle. Information about the infrastructure is necessary for the vehicle's TARA yet the vehicle's manufacturer lacks such information to estimate the effort needed to perform such an action. Using the concept of a d-asset, the dependency between the vehicle and the smart infrastructure can be represented since it allows the vehicle's TARA to quantify the effort needed to steal the certificate through rating the d-asset, representing a requirement for secure connection when interfacing with an external system. Therefore in this example, the d-asset is *steal the infrastructure security certificate*.

Furthermore, a security property is associated to the d-asset, in this case it is confidentiality. We derived this security property from the d-asset since the infrastructure security certificate needs to not be accessed by unauthorized parties to protect its confidentiality.

d) *Threats*: We model a stereotype for security threats, which can cause harm if the properties associated with an asset are violated. This modeling uses a stereotype with two attributes: the description of the threat and the associated asset which can be violated.

e) *Dependency Matrix for Traceability*: Traceability, a key concept in MBSE, maintains the relationship between artifacts and system model elements, ensuring model consistency and facilitating change tracing. We employ a SysML generic table to provide an overview of linked system elements, an example is shown in Fig.6. The figure displays as an example

Fig. 5. Attack Path Example

the generic table of assets alongside their description, linked component and security properties.

Since the proposed method is not intended to model complete TARAs including all of their elements, we focus to model the needed elements that are required by the different phases of the method. Each of these TARA elements can be modeled using the developed SysML profile in Cameo Systems Modeler [20].

Upon completing the first phase of TARA modeling, the model is exported into a machine readable format. It is exported as an XML file which serves as the input for the next phase.

B. Second Phase - Processing

In the second phase, the information of the exported TARA model is processed over two stages. The first stage parses the XML file saving the information in an XML Metadata Interchange (XMI) structure while the second stage applies the compatibility conditions.

1) *XML Parsing*: The primary objective of the first stage is to parse each of the modeled TARAs encoded in the XML files. The desired outcome is to extract the information required by the method in the following phase. This information is in the form of TARA elements required for evaluating the compatibility conditions such as assets, d-assets, security properties, threats, attack paths, and attack path rating. Also, it is in the form of the relationships between the different TARA elements.

We developed a Python parser to process the XML files exported from a SysML model. The following steps describe the function of the developed script.

a) *XML File Reading*: The first step of the parser is to read the XML file, which contains the exported SysML model in an XMI format. XMI allows representing the structured data in a human-readable and machine-readable format. It is often used in conjunction with modeling languages like UML or SysML.

b) *Root Element Identification*: The parser identifies the root element of the SysML model in the XML file. In XML, the root element is the top-level element of the XML file, it encapsulates all other elements in the file. This root element is used as a starting point to analyze the structure of the XML file.

c) *Traversing the XML Structure*: The parser traverses the hierarchy of the XML structure, moving from the root element to its child elements.

d) *Relationship Identification*: The parser identifies the relationships between the different elements within the XML file. This is done using the *xmi:id* attribute. The *xmi:id* is an attribute commonly used in XML that follows the XMI standard. It is a unique identifier for an element that distinguishes

different elements from one another. Moreover, the *xmi:id* attribute allows elements within the XML to be linked or referenced to each other, which enables forming relationships between the different elements. The parser uses the *xmi:id* attribute to identify which elements are related to each other through comparing the value of the element's *xmi:id* attribute to that of the other element. If a match is found, then the parser identifies the relationship between both elements.

e) *Element Extraction*: The parser extracts the target XMI elements such as *Attack Path*, *Threat* and *Assets*. For each element found, the parser proceeds to extract the elements information, such as name, attributes and values. The first target element in the XML is *Attack Path*. The parser code searches for and extracts every instance of *Attack Path* and saves the *xmi:id* attribute value of each instance found. Moreover, the parser extracts and saves the values of the attributes of attack path rating which are *TIME*, *EXPERTISE*, *KNOWLEDGE*, *ACCESS* and *EQUIPMENT*. The last attribute to extract and save its value is *Threat*. Using the *xmi:id* attribute, all of the extracted attributes are linked to their corresponding attack path through adding the *xmi:id* as a suffix to their names.

The next target element is *d-asset*, the parser code uses *xmi:id* of the attack path to search the nested elements inside every attack path. The nested elements are actions, if the action is a *d-asset*, the parser code extracts and saves the value of the attributes of the *d-asset* element which are the name and the *xmi:id* of the d-asset. The parser code uses the *xmi:id* value of the d-asset to extract the security property of the *d-asset* element, the *CIL* attribute values and d-asset rating.

Afterwards, the parser code searches for the element *Asset* using the value of the attribute *Threat*, previously extracted from the *Attack Path* target element. After finding the target element *Asset*, the parser code, in a similar fashion to the *d-asset* element, uses the *xmi:id* attribute value to extract and save the security properties of the *Asset* in addition to *CIL* attribute values.

In summary, the parser code begins with extracting attack paths, from which it saves the attribute values of attack path rating, threat and *xmi:id*. After that, the code uses the *xmi:id* of attack paths to extract d-assets, then their security properties, rating and their CIL. Also, the parser uses the attribute value of the extracted threats to extract the assets followed by their security properties and CIL.

f) *Data Structure Organization*: Once the parser extracted all the needed data from the XML files, it organizes this information into a JSON file, which consists of key-value pairs, dictionaries and lists. This data structure allows for easy access and manipulation of the data to apply the compatibility conditions in the coming steps. The JSON file contains the following extracted information: assets, d-assets, security properties, threats, CIL, d-asset rating, attack paths and attack path rating. The data in the JSON file is structured into two group types. The first group type is *Group (d-asset)* and the second is *Group (asset)*, an example of the group types is shown in Fig.7.

The data in the JSON file is saved in a dictionary of

#	Name	Description	Component	Property
1	Asset_Vehicle_1	This describes information about the vehicle as provided by the sensors	Wi-Fi	confidentiality integrity
2	Asset_Vehicle_2	The CAN bus is available for vehicle communication	CAN Bus	availability

Fig. 6. Example of Generic Table of Assets

key-value pairs, each pair contains an entry of the extracted information and its corresponding value. The entries of the first group type include the d-asset name, value, security property and rating in addition to the CIL value. While the second group type include asset name, value, security property and the attack path rating in addition to CIL value as well. Note that the information is grouped according to the *xmi:id* and the identified relationships in the previous steps of 4.Relationship Identification and 5.Element Extraction. The number of groups of each type corresponds to the number of threats.

It is worth noting that the content of the JSON file is the essential information that needs to be exchanged between two manufacturers to check if their subsystems are compatible. Any information in a TARA beyond this information does not have to be disclosed to other parties. This saves manufacturers from sharing unnecessary information or intellectual property. Moreover, we display the JSON data, referred to in the figures, in such format to allow for a understandable compatibility statement and to simplify understanding.

2) *Compatibility Conditions*: The second stage of the processing phase is to apply the conditions of compatibility to the previously grouped information. We use the compatibility conditions of Abdelsalam et al. [1] referred to previously in section III. These conditions help determine whether the two subsystems under evaluation are compatible to work securely together or not.

The compatibility conditions use three TARA elements for the evaluation, d-assets and assets, security properties, and ratings. The code starts comparing these TARA elements of the first group type, *Group (d-asset)*, to the corresponding TARA elements of the second group type *Group (asset)*. Each group of the first group type is compared to each group of the second type.

In applying the compatibility conditions on two different group types, the comparison is made between the d-assets of the first subsystem to the assets of the second subsystem. Starting with the first condition, the code checks the CIL values since it is used to relate the d-asset of one subsystem to the asset of another.

The second condition checks the security properties of every matched d-asset and asset. The last condition of *Rating Condition* checks if all five attributes of the d-asset rating are less than or equal to the corresponding attribute rating of the asset attack path.

Two subsystems are compatible once they satisfy all three of the compatibility conditions. To achieve full compatibility

```

"GroupName": "Group 1 (d-asset)",
"GroupData": {
  "d-asset_Name": "AttackPaths_Vehicle_1_d-asset_1",
  "d-asset_Value": "infrastructure correct information",
  "d-asset_Security_Properties": "integrity",
  "d-asset_CIL": "Info List",
  "d-asset_Ratings": {
    "time__2021x_1_79b01ef_1704368536761_309086_17806": "<= 1 month - Value = 4",
    "expertise__2021x_1_79b01ef_1704368536761_309086_17806": "proficient - Value = 3",
    "knowledge__2021x_1_79b01ef_1704368536761_309086_17806": "restricted - Value = 3",
    "access__2021x_1_79b01ef_1704368536761_309086_17806": "easy - Value = 1",
    "equipment__2021x_1_79b01ef_1704368536761_309086_17806": "standard - Value = 3"
  }
}

```

Fig. 7. Example of *Group (d-asset)* data in The JSON File

between two subsystems, all d-assets of both subsystems must be considered as assets by the other subsystem in addition to satisfying the associated security property and attack path rating conditions.

C. Third Phase - Data Compilation

The final phase of the method compiles all the data from the previous phases to generate a compatibility statement. The code checks the result of each condition before printing it to the compatibility statement to determine the compatibility of the two subsystems. The statement displays the TARA information of each respective subsystem, such as d-asset, asset, security property and ratings. Moreover, the results of the compatibility conditions are displayed stating whether they were satisfied or not. Finally, it provides a verdict about the security compatibility of the two subsystems in addition to the reasons of incompatibility if applicable. Such a statement aids the user of our method to take a better-informed decision about connecting the two subsystems under evaluation.

In Fig.8 is an abstract representation of an example compatibility statement. The statement starts by displaying the d-asset and asset compared in the *Assets Condition*. It displays their names and the result of the evaluation condition.

Compatibility Statement:

d-asset_{Vehicle}: AttackPaths_Vehicle_1_d-asset_1,
asset_{Infrastructure}: Assets_Infrastructure_1,
Assets Condition: True

d-asset Security Property_{Vehicle}: Integrity,
asset Security Property_{Infrastructure}: Integrity,
Security Property Condition: True

Rating_{Vehicle} = {4, 3, 3, 1, 3},
Rating_{Infrastructure} = {4, 3, 7, 1, 3},
Rating Condition: True

Verdict:

Subsystems Vehicle & Infrastructure are compatible.

Reason(s) for incompatibility:

N/A

Fig. 8. Compatibility Statement Example

The statement also shows the security properties of the compared d-asset and asset in addition to the ratings of the respective attack paths and d-assets. Finally, a verdict is generated stating that the two subsystems of the vehicle and the infrastructure are compatible since in the given figure, the three conditions were satisfied.

In summary, we built upon and improved the different phases of the C-TAR method [1]. We improved the method by transforming it from a theoretical concept into an actual implementation. In the C-TAR method, the process of how to input two different TARAs to their method was unspecified. In our work, we provide a SysML profile to develop a uniform way of TARA input into our method.

Moreover, they proposed primary steps to extract the needed information from a TARA and apply the compatibility conditions to it, but their work was lacking an implementation. Using these steps, we built upon and improved them to develop

a script for processing the TARA input information and parse it. This allowed us to extract the needed data from the modeled TARA and apply the compatibility conditions to it. Also, we developed a script that checks the applied conditions and accordingly generates a compatibility statement inspired by their proposed statement.

V. METHOD EVALUATION

This section evaluates the method functionality by applying it to a real industrial use case. We acquired two industrial TARAs developed by Robert Bosch GmbH to apply our method. In the following sections we apply our method to the use case and evaluate the obtained results.

A. Subsystems Description

The given use case consists of two subsystems. The first subsystem is a vehicle while the second is an infrastructure system. Both subsystems form an overall system shown in Fig.9. The infrastructure subsystem observes the entry of a tunnel and the surrounding areas. Using its sensors, the infrastructure system is able to detect objects in the surrounding area. A local Road Side Unit (RSU) compiles a list of detected objects, their dimensions and speed, and information about the sensors. This list is sent as a Collective Perception Message (CPM) [24] to the vehicle. By utilizing the content of the object list, the vehicle makes autonomous driving decisions.

Fig. 9. Use Case System Overview

Note that in this paper we cannot disclose all of the details about the subsystems or their security analysis as this would reveal far reaching details about design decisions of the subsystem. In order to protect this intellectual property, we anonymize the details. Nevertheless we provide the necessary information needed for the context of this paper.

B. Modeling the TARAs

For each subsystem, vehicle and infrastructure, we had a TARA available, which was provided by the engineers developing the two subsystems. These original TARAs were modeled using the TARA tool CycurRISK [25]. In order to apply our method, we re-modeled these TARAs in Cameo [20] using our SysML profile as described in Section IV-A3. In particular, we created one TARA in Cameo for the vehicle, and one for the infrastructure system. Since for the purpose of our evaluation, it is not relevant to model the entire TARA, we limited the re-modeling to the following TARA elements: assets, security properties, threats, attack paths and attack path and d-assets ratings.

We limited the modeling of attack paths to those, which expressed a dependency on an external system (i.e., the infrastructure or the vehicle). We identified an action in these attack paths as a d-asset if two conditions were satisfied: If there is not enough information about the action to rate it and if the missing information depends on the other system. We modeled all actions that matched these criteria as d-assets. The security properties of each d-asset were deduced from the context of the actions.

In the original vehicle TARA, seven assets were modeled, and twelve threats and one attack tree per threat. The assets identified in the vehicle TARA are related to the autonomous driving decisions made by the vehicle. In the vehicle TARA, we modeled the same seven assets, three attack paths, where each contained one d-asset. We omitted modeling the other attack paths from the vehicle TARA. That is because the other attack paths in the vehicle TARA did not depend on the infrastructure system and the infrastructure TARA did not contain a dependency on the vehicle TARA.

For each attack path we assigned the rating which we were able to directly gain from the original TARAs. For each d-asset, we provided the rating such that the attack path containing the d-asset is not the easiest attack path for the related threat. This way, the easiest way to realize a threat does not depend on the external system (infrastructure) but only the vehicle.

The original infrastructure TARA modeled eleven assets, fifteen threats and attack trees. Out of these assets, we only modeled the two assets which were related to the d-assets of the vehicle TARA. The two assets we modeled were information transmitted in the CPMs from the infrastructure to the vehicle about the current state of the environment. For each of these assets, the security properties availability and integrity were considered to be relevant for the system's security. We did not identify any d-assets in the infrastructure TARA, since the infrastructure does not process information received from the vehicle or have actions that depend on the vehicle. Additionally, we modeled one attack path for each threat, i.e. in total four.

We would like to note that in practice, the entire TARA would have to be modeled. We only omitted elements from the TARAs, which do not influence the outcome of the method with respect to the compatibility of the two subsystems.

The two subsystems in our case communicate via the CPM protocol [24], so we defined the CIL based on the definition of this protocol. In particular, CPM defines for example the data fields *SensorInformationContainer*, *PerceptionRegion-Container* and *PerceivedObjectContainer*, which we added to the CIL. Each asset in the infrastructure TARA and each d-asset in the vehicle TARA represent a specific data field from the CPM protocol, so we assigned them the corresponding CIL element.

C. Compatibility Statement

We took the exported XML files of each subsystem and applied the parser code. The code parsed the information, ap-

plied the compatibility conditions and successfully generated the compatibility statement. In a first run, one of the three conditions was not satisfied, therefore, the two subsystems were not compatible according to our method. The compatibility statement contained details about all of the conditions. This allowed us to review the reasons of incompatibility easily.

We deduced from our analysis, that there was a mismatch in the security properties of an asset and the corresponding d-asset. For an asset in the infrastructure which models the status of the environment, the security property integrity was modeled, while for the corresponding d-asset the security property confidentiality was accidentally modeled. This finding indicates that the attacker can gain knowledge about the environment status from the infrastructure, since its confidentiality is not protected. This knowledge can then be used to attack the vehicle.

After identifying this mismatch, the error in our modeling was easily corrected and the new statement stated that the two subsystems are compatible.

D. Evaluation Results

Applying the method to a given TARA is straightforward, the main effort needed was in the TARA modeling phase as the two remaining phases were automated. In the modeling phase, we had to manually identify the d-assets, their security properties and their CIL values from the given TARA. The information we needed for such step was all modeled in each subsystem's TARA. In the application of our method, the modeling step was fairly simple.

The effort required for modeling depends on the complexity of the TARA, in our use case this was 2-3 hours for each TARA. The main challenges faced were extracting the d-assets from the TARA and rating the d-asset as it requires an understanding of the attack path the d-asset is a part of.

The original TARAs of the subsystems we used were modeled according to requirements by the ISO/SAE 21434 [13] standard. It was fairly straightforward to model these TARAs in Cameo to the extent required for our evaluation of the method, this indicates that the SysML profile is suitable to model TARAs consistent with the industry standard.

The generated compatibility statement provided useful insights about the subsystems compatibility. Starting with the first condition, if there is no matching asset to a d-asset, this means that the d-asset in one TARA was not considered as an asset in the other TARA, meaning that it is not protected. In our use case, all d-assets of a TARA were considered as assets in the other TARA. Each asset need to have the security properties of the d-asset it is compared to. The compatibility statement stated that this was not satisfied for one of the d-assets resulting in incompatible subsystems. Through checking the attack path rating, we are able to deduce that there is no attack path of an asset that requires less effort than the effort assumed by the d-asset rating.

After identifying the incompatibility of our subsystems, the detailed description of the compatibility statement helped us to easily identify the underlying problem with our two

subsystems. It directly pointed out which information was not protected by the infrastructure but expected to be protected by the vehicle. Finding and correcting the little modeling mistake was therefore a matter of minutes.

We do not discuss in detail what happens in case of incompatibility, however, one can image a wide range of options. When checks are performed during development, functionality of the systems can be adapted. If the checks are performed during runtime, one system can choose to refuse cooperation, use other systems if support is required, or downgrade the system's functionality based on the security analysis.

While the proposed method possesses several strengths, it is not without some limitations. Firstly, testing the method was done on two industrial use cases so far, therefore, further studies with diverse use cases are needed to enhance the method's applicability. Secondly, the evaluation of the subsystems' compatibility is highly dependent on the provided TARA elements. Moreover, the TARA modeling phase is mostly a manual process in the method which could be erroneous in some cases, specially in much larger systems. Developing an automated process of translating a TARA into the SysML model could prove beneficial in improving the method's ease of use and producing error-free TARA models.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a novel method for analyzing the security compatibility of distributed systems. We developed a SysML profile, that enables its user to model TARA elements of a subsystem in addition to elements specific to the method such as d-assets and our developed concept of CIL. The SysML profile allows representing dependencies to external systems using d-assets, which express an assumption on an asset and its security property which has to be ensured by an external system.

Furthermore, our method allows the exchange of information between manufacturers to check for the compatibility of their systems using the proposed JSON files. The information included is limited to a minimum, so that detailed design decisions and intellectual property of a system are protected.

We evaluated our method on a real-world system consisting of an autonomous vehicle, which cooperates with a safety-critical intelligent infrastructure system. Our evaluation shows that modeling a TARA using our method is not significantly more complicated or time-consuming than modeling the TARA conventionally according to ISO/SAE 21434 guidelines. The compatibility check, and its resulting report, is suitable to analyze causes of incompatibility and allows for reactions based on it.

We expect our method to be especially useful to evaluate systems in the context of Intelligent Transport Systems, while developers of each system do not know about the potential cooperation partner at design time or when cooperating system configurations change over time.

For future work, incorporating the parser code and the compatibility conditions into the SysML tool would reduce the manual effort and time required, enhancing the efficiency

of the overall method. Also, scaling the implementation to be applied to more than two subsystems at the same time.

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